

Casanova Drift Model (CDM)

User Manual

Version 1.0

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1. Introduction

This User Manual (UM) provides the information necessary for both internal and external users to effectively use the Casanova Drift Model (CDM).

Today's pesticide risk assessments rely either on drift tables or screening levels models that result in excessively large, unrealistic buffer zones. Field studies provide real-world exposure assessment but are limited because they can capture only select application and environmental parameters. Two models already exist (SiMod, UK; IDEFICS, NL). Neither are truly in the public domain, nor is the code available for outside development or scrutiny. CDM is a higher-tier arable crop drift deposition that is validated, open-source, and has a user-friendly accessible interface.

1.1 Overview

The CDM was originally developed in-house by Ed Casanova (ex-Monsanto, now in Bayer's Enabling Technology Team) as a tool for screening formulations to limit field trials. It was programmed in not user-friendly MathCad without a user interface (UI). The CDM working group has converted and further developed the core functions in C++ and added an R package together with a shiny UI to make it more user-friendly and can be employed by non-programmers.

The model is calibrated and validated against the Spray Drift Task Force arable data sets and then against internal field trial data.

Principal components of the model

- Droplet size distribution (DSD) – temporal data and at operating pressure to be modelled.
- Nozzle flow vs. pressure (velocity of droplet obtained here)
- Tank solution density, total dissolved solids (DS) concentration, and check between intended application rate (IAR) for active, DS, NF, and Tractor speed (TS) (also important for evaporation).
- Determination of wet bulb T depression (DTwb) for use in droplet evaporation equation
- Wind velocity profile with elevation and horizontal variability in wind direction around mean relative to sprayed field – turbulence in direction of wind only. (Remaining two dimensions to be added.)
- Deposition of droplets – converted to a deposition curve.

1.2 Installation

CDM can be installed locally in your Window environment. It is also accessible via deployed shiny apps. Currently the deployed version on IZ tenant is decommissioned due to the IT separation between PH CH and CS.

To be able to use CDM c++ library, there is no specific prerequisites. However, if you need to use the shiny UI and the R package, you need R installation and preferably RStudio installation in your environment. On Windows, you need to install [Rtools](#) for the compilation of R package.

Installation under Window 10 or 11

1. Go to the [cdmcpp GitHub repository](#) to download the latest windows build artefact of the library. You can find it in the hosted-build github actions, an example is <https://github.com/bayer-int/cdmcpp/actions/runs/7806215997>.

← hosted-build

✓ Add new command-line interface and API function `cdm_library_version`. #14

Summary

Jobs

- ✓ ubuntu-latest-hosted-build
- ✓ macos-latest-hosted-build
- ✓ windows-latest-hosted-build

Run details

- Usage
- Workflow file

Triggered via push 3 months ago	Status	Total duration	Billable time	Artifacts
jbuonagurio pushed <code>e61ad0b</code> <code>master</code>	Success	47m 59s	1h 38m	3

hosted-build.yml

on: push

Matrix: job

- ✓ macos-latest-hosted-b... 26m 47s
- ✓ ubuntu-latest-hosted-b... 22m 42s
- ✓ windows-latest-hosted-... 47m 43s

- Unpack `windows-latest.hosted.zip`, the command line version will already work.
- To install the corresponding R package, you need to go to the release tags to find the release the package source archive. Unpack it to a folder, e.g., `~/cdm`.
- Suppose you have a folder `cdm` under your HOME directory, then copy `libcdm.dll` to `./cdm/R/cdm/inst/libs/x64`
- Install the R packages within RStudio using the following command.

```
install.packages("~/cdm/R/cdm", repos=NULL, type="source", INSTALL_opts="--no-multiarch")
```

- To install the shiny UI, go to the [GitHub repository](#) to download the latest source archive.
- Now open RStudio, you can either install the shiny app as an R package or directly run from console.

2. Getting Started

Before you start, please familiar your self with the example input json files below, which include all the relevant user inputs that are necessary to run the model.

2.1 Example Input json Files

Model input files are included for the following SETAC DRAW test cases (link to github files):

Case	Trial ID	Nozzle Type	Nozzle Pressure	Surfactant	Input File
B	FR_1_017	AXI 11002	250 kPa (36 psig)	None	Case B.json
G	NL_1_660	XR 11004	300 kPa (44 psig)	Agral	Case G.json
I	DE_4_006	XR 11004	250 kPa (36 psig)	None	Case I.json

2.2 A general walkthrough of CDM

Instructions: Briefly describe and graphically depict as appropriate the equipment, communications, and network configuration of the system in a way that a non-technical user can understand. Include the type of computer input and output devices. Describe any set-up considerations.

Example using R or RStudio

```

> library(cdm)
> demo()
> demo("caseB")

demo(caseB)
---- ~~~~~

Type <Return> to start :

> ### *- R -*
> require(cdm)

> config.file <- system.file("extdata", "Case_B.json", package="cdm")

> config <- readChar(config.file, file.info(config.file)$size)

> output <- cdm(config)

> print(jsonlite::fromJSON(output))
[[1]]
[1] "Case_B"

[[2]]
[[2]]$dropletSizeDistribution
      [,1]      [,2]
[1,]   18 4.772e-05
[2,]   22 1.185e-03
[3,]   26 2.874e-03
[4,]   30 4.877e-03
[5,]   36 8.392e-03
[6,]   44 1.423e-02
[7,]   52 2.166e-02
[8,]   62 3.351e-02
[9,]   74 5.180e-02
[10,]  86 7.467e-02
[11,] 100 1.067e-01
[12,] 120 1.611e-01
[13,] 150 2.553e-01
[14,] 180 3.555e-01
[15,] 210 4.540e-01
[16,] 250 5.742e-01
[17,] 300 6.992e-01
[18,] 360 8.106e-01
[19,] 410 8.758e-01
[20,] 500 9.472e-01
[21,] 600 9.837e-01
[22,] 720 9.983e-01
[23,] 860 1.000e+00

[[2]]$dryAirTemperature
[1] 16.6

[[2]]$barometricPressure
[1] 101325

[[2]]$relativeHumidity

```

Figure 1: Example Screenshot of Running the model in R environment.

Example run using Shiny UI

To fire up the UI locally, you can either install the shiny package or just using the code below:

```
devtools::load_all()  
run_app()
```

1. Go to the Data Input page as shown in Figure 2, input your data file as a json input, or a json file plus a DSD csv file. You can also start using an example dataset from the dropdown menu. Go through each tab to check if you have everything correctly set.

The screenshot shows the 'Data Input' page of the Casanova Drift Model (CDM). The page is titled 'Manually Input or Edit Parameters' and features four tabs: 'Environmental Settings', 'Wind Profile', 'Application Settings', and 'Advanced Settings'. The 'Advanced Settings' tab is currently selected. On the left side, there are three sections for configuration: 'Provide Name for Analysis' with a text input field containing 'Name of scenariak'; 'Choose Dataset' with a dropdown menu showing 'Example'; and 'Regulatory Scenario' with a dropdown menu showing 'User defined'. The main content area of the 'Advanced Settings' tab contains three input fields: 'Dry air temperature [°C]' with the value '15', 'Dry air barometric pressure [Pa]' with the value '101325', and 'Relative humidity [percent]' with the value '81'.

Figure 2: Screen shot of data input

2. Move to the Calculations page (as shown in Figure 3), click on the “Calculate” button. All relevant output will be shown on the UI in tabbed format. You can check each tab for the output. You also download the relevant results from the different download buttons. Report file is available in HTML and Word format.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the calculation page

2.3 Accessing the deployed UI

To be added after new deploxment.

3. Using CDM on IZ tenant

Note this part does not apply anymore as the tenant is decommissioned in 2023 and many of the online documentation is not available anymore.

The user access to the app on Bayer IZ tenant is managed via [PAPI groups membership](#). Please contact the owners of the group for adding you as a member if you are a Bayer employee.

More about API keys:

<https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/API+Key+management>

Endpoint description : <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/Endpoints>

On QA platform apart from default S3 buckets for you tenant you will find services like EMR, K8S and Docker Jobs.

Access to IZ:

There are three main ways to manage your tenant resources on IZ QA.

1. Access thru AWS console (<http://go/aws>) and you primary CWID controlled by PAPI groups (you are owner of corresponding groups):
 - <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/cdm>
 - <https://devtools.bayer.com/docs/authorization/papi/workflows/owner/adding>
2. Access thru API endpoints – manage of selected services:
 - <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/Endpoints>
3. Access thru AWS SSO – access to AWS CLI also with corresponding PAPI group:
 - <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=361170361>
 - <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=358482033>

Default tenant setup on AWS:

Your tenant apart from set dedicated IAM roles and policies has as well default S3 buckets created:

Object description	Name	Additional info
S3 bucket	for ingesting data (RAW)	iz-<tenant>-bucket-raw-<reg>-<env>
	for output data (Result)	iz-<tenant>-bucket-result-<reg>-<env>
	for storing / publishing logs	iz-<tenant>-bucket-log-<reg>-<env>
	for storing backups	iz-<tenant>-bucket-backup-<reg>-<env>
	for config files, bootstrap scripts etc	iz-<tenant>-bucket-config-<reg>-<env>
	for ssh keys	iz-<tenant>-bucket-keys-<reg>-<env>

<reg> - eu for eu-central-1 or us for us-east-1 or ap-southeast-1

<env> - qa for IZ QA environment

We can make connection to other S3 buckets – let us know what it should be.

We can also establish dedicated connection via VPC endpoint – also let us know if you need it.

You will find most important AWS endpoints(K8s cluster, WAF, ECR, etc) used on IZ under that link:

<https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/Cross+tenants+settings>

There is also mentioned how to get that information via API call.

K8S:

There is shared K8S cluster with tenant dedicated namespace: “cdm” and corresponding services accounts, limits quotas, etc.

Suggested way is to connect to cluster via kubectl using AWS SSO:

- <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=361170361>
- <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=358482033>

K8S description, high level setup: <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/Shared+Kubernetes+cluster>

Few examples of using K8S:

- <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/How+to+setup+pipeline+on+Gitlab+that+deploys+on+EKS>
- <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/How+to+run+web+ui+app+on+EKS>
- <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/How+to+deploy+job+on+EKS>

Ingress rule creation:

<https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/How+to+create+shared+Ingress+with+enabled+authentication>

Route53 record for K8s:

<https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/How+to+create+and+manage+DNS+records+for+K8S+Ingress+rule>

Different types of nodes: <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/How+to+run+Pods+on+dedicated+nodes>

Others: <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=369000571>

Please contact with Andris – dedicated S@S person for K8s

Airflow on K8S:

In order to make Airflow deployment for you we will need from you:

- Gitlab user + gitlab token and URL to your repo where DAG's will be stored
- Azure AD app.registry id and secret to access it (we can create that for you and link to your tenant PAPI group)

EMR:

Similar to EZ (Exploration Zone), a EMR cluster is available on EZ as well. You can have a one cluster running in EU and one in US.

Endpoint description : <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/Endpoints>,

Service description: <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/EMR+cluster>

EMR idle detection: <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/EMR+idle+detection>

Access to EMR Spark UI: <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/EMR+Spark+UI>

EMR Notebook: <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/EMR+Notebook>

Dockerjobs:

This works very similar to EZ option.

End to end process description: <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/SAS/CS+-+End-to-End%3A+How+to+use+Docker+backed+Jobs> (note that examples are based on EZ platform)

High level information and description: <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/Docker+backed+jobs>

How to run docker job: <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/How+to+run+Docker+Backed+Jobs>

Additional features on IZ are related to log access from AWS console and alerting.

Log access: <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/Batch+jobs+log+processing>

Scheduling rules: <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/How+to+schedule+docker+job>

Alerting: <https://wiki.intranet.cnb/display/IZ/How+to+setup+an+alert+based+on+Cloud+Watch+logs>

4. Troubleshooting & Support

4.1 Support

If you need to report a bug or request new features,

Table 1 - Support Points of Contact

Contact	Organization	Email	Role	Responsibility
Zhenglei Gao	DSDT	Zhenglei.gao@bayer.com	System Owner	Issue management

Install dependencies:

```

.\vcpkg\vcpkg install blaze:x64-windows-static
.\vcpkg\vcpkg install boost-math:x64-windows-static
.\vcpkg\vcpkg install fmt:x64-windows-static
.\vcpkg\vcpkg install nlohmann-json:x64-windows-static
.\vcpkg\vcpkg install ceres:x64-windows-static
.\vcpkg\vcpkg install sundials:x64-windows-static

```

Clone this repository and build CDM:

```

git clone --branch cpp https://gitlab.bayer.com/GBBFX/mondep.git ./cdm
cmake -B ./cdm/build -S ./cdm -G Ninja -DCMAKE_BUILD_TYPE=Release -
DBUILD_SHARED_LIBS=On -
DCMAKE_TOOLCHAIN_FILE=%USERPROFILE%\vcpkg\scripts\buildsystems\vcpkg.cmake -
DVCPKG_TARGET_TRIPLET=x64-windows-static
cmake --build ./cdm/build

```

The model library (libcdm.dll) and command-line executable (cdmcli.exe) will be located in the ./cdm/bin directory. If you are using the R package, copy libcdm.dll to ./cdm/R/cdm/inst/libs/x64:

```
copy ./cdm/bin/libcdm.dll ./cdm/R/cdm/inst/libs/x64
```

Build on Linux with vcpkg

Install C++ development tools and Git using the package management tool that comes with your Linux distribution. On a Debian-based distribution, such as Ubuntu, use APT:

```

sudo apt update
sudo apt install build-essential git-all

```

Follow the instructions at apt.kitware.com to install the latest version of CMake using APT. For alternative installation options, see cmake.org/download.

Install vcpkg as follows, assuming it will be installed in your home directory (~):

```

cd ~
git clone https://github.com/microsoft/vcpkg
.\vcpkg/bootstrap-vcpkg.sh

```

Install dependencies:

```

.\vcpkg\vcpkg install blaze:x64-linux
.\vcpkg\vcpkg install boost-math:x64-linux
.\vcpkg\vcpkg install fmt:x64-linux
.\vcpkg\vcpkg install nlohmann-json:x64-linux
.\vcpkg\vcpkg install ceres:x64-linux
.\vcpkg\vcpkg install sundials:x64-linux

```

Clone this repository, build and install CDM:

```

git clone --branch cpp https://gitlab.bayer.com/GBBFX/mondep.git ./cdm
cmake -B ./cdm/build -S ./cdm -DCMAKE_BUILD_TYPE=Release -
DBUILD_SHARED_LIBS=On -

```

```
DCMAKE_TOOLCHAIN_FILE=~/.vcpkg/scripts/buildsystems/vcpkg.cmake -  
DVCPKG_TARGET_TRIPLET=x64-linux  
cmake --build ./cdm/build  
cmake --install ./cdm/build
```

The header file (CDM.h), library (libcdm.so), and executable (cdmcli) are copied to /usr/local/include/cdm, /usr/local/lib64 and /usr/local/bin respectively.

6. Legal Notices

6.1 Disclaimer

Currently CDM is mainly used internally.

6.2 License

7. Appendix

7.1 Appendix A: Record of Changes

Table 2 - Record of Changes

Version Number	Date	Author/Owner	Description of Change
1.0	23.08.2023	Zhenglei Gao	First release of CDM
1.0	01.03.2024	Zhenglei Gao	Updated installation procedures

7.2 Appendix B: Glossary

Table 3 - Glossary

Term	Acronym	Definition
Casanova Drift Model	CDM	The name of the drift model
Crop Science	CS	Crop Science Division
<Term>	<Acronym>	<Definition>